

PROSPECTIVE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS, THE ENTRY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN INTO THE RANKS OF DEVELOPED COUNTRIES

Jabborov Umidjon Sotiboldiyevich

Tashkent Financial Institute, Department of Physical Education and Sports Activities

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7854334>

Abstract: The independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan was an important period of the new sovereign state. Naturally, a new stage in the development of physical culture and sports has begun, which is moving forward with the development of society. The future development of physical culture and sports is inextricably linked with the concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan joining the ranks of developed countries, building a democratic state, the transition to market relations. This article examines the importance of sports training as a pedagogical process.

Keywords: education, sports training, physical education, healthy lifestyle, sports, harmoniously developed generation, valeology, sports competitions.

Physical culture and sports have always been an integral part of the development of society. The social communities that existed before us also attached great importance to physical education and sports in their development. Physical culture and sports served to represent the interests of the ruling classes in society, defended it and guided them. Sports training is a pedagogical process aimed primarily at the full development of the individual. The content and methods of the process of preparation for sports training should be appropriate to the age, gender and level of training of the athlete, as well as take into account the climate, specific climatic features, location, conditions.

Physical culture, physical education and sports are important factors not only in physical but also in spiritual development. It heals the will, teaches to strive for a clear goal, to endure difficulties with endurance and perseverance. It instills in the human heart confidence, pride and pride in victory. The training program for sports should gradually become more complex, increasing or improving in a moderate way, without suddenly increasing both in the amount of exercise and in strength. There are processes that are important for the comprehensive development of sports and the further popularization of important aspects of training. The main focus on sports and its popularity is formed on the basis of human responsibility to society from time immemorial. At the same time, special attention is paid to physical culture and "peace of mind", which is one of its important stages. This is evidenced by the fact that the main task of young athletes is to pay attention to peace of mind.

Sports games are the highest stage of the development of outdoor games. They differ from mobile ones by uniform rules that determine the composition of participants, the size and layout of the site, the duration of the game, equipment and inventory, etc., which allows holding competitions of various scales. Competitions in sports games are of the nature of wrestling and require a lot of physical exertion and strong-willed efforts from the participants. Young sportsman's intellectual training in sports games is mentioned in the

article. There are also given the most important information about the development of intellectual abilities, with mental functions such as memory, attention, critical thinking, perception and others.

Orientation to higher sportsmanship.

a) This requirement teaches the student-athlete to strive for the sport and its achievements, especially the record. The means and methods of organizing sports exercises and organizing lessons should be aimed at this goal. This is because coaches plan classes for students from the beginning of the school year based on their living, family circumstances and opportunities.

b) inseparability of general and special physical training - general and special physical training of an athlete is inseparable. Athlete's readiness for training can be determined by the indicator of sports results. The purpose of regular exercise is to strengthen health, increase the level of functional capacity of the body. In one-year planning, in the early stages of the preparatory period, special physical training takes the lead in increasing the workload, first even general physical training, and then even if the workload is increased;

c) continuity of the process of sports training. To achieve effective sports activities, you need to exercise regularly. Unreasonable cessation of exercise leads to a decrease in physical qualities during training (this applies to the qualities of endurance, flexibility and agility);

g) striving to do the largest amount of work. Modern sports performance involves the gradual performance of high loads. The main condition for this is to maintain the functional capacity of the body to adapt, the transition from one to two to three sessions a day should be gradual.

Wave dynamic work. This work is based on fatigue and recovery after exercise. Therefore, the whole training process (the training itself or part of it) should be structured based on working at wave speed. There must be sports competitions when it comes to physical education. The competition can have different levels according to their specialization. The participation of students in mass races, swimming, bicycle races, etc. will be intensified. Participation in competitions encourages physical culture, coverage of public competitions in newspapers and magazines, radio and television are of great importance in the promotion of the mass physical culture movement.

Sports clubs have a specific daily program, which includes competitions and reporting, and most importantly, a comparative review of the results of competitions.

The choice of athletes can be divided into several types:

a) within the educational institution - on the basis of the Spartakiad program, inter-faculty competitions are held.

b) by educational institutions - between urban higher education institutions, within the region or independent states. The main goal is to select the most talented athletes to participate in international competitions.

c) international - can be different (including the Asian Championship or Championship, European, World, Olympic Games, Universiade). These competitions can be held once a year, once every two to three to four years. The Olympic Games are held once every 4 years in summer and winter.

CONCLUSION.

The main task is to set and record the strongest athletes from the continent or the world, as well as to determine the purpose and mission of the sport. One of the methods of sports training is called competitive. Indeed, the role of competition in sports training is enormous.

First and foremost, in the process of such an exercise, accuracy, honesty is tested and appropriately assessed.

References:

1. Tashpulatov F. A., Shermatov G. K. Wrestling–The Honor of Uzbek Nation //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – Т. 8. – С. 205-208.
2. Alisherovich T. F. Sog'lom turmush tarzini shakillantirishda jismoniy madaniyatning inson hayotidagi roli //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – С. 187-190.
3. Ташпулатов Ф. ГАНДОЛЧИЛАР О'ЙИН FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI HAR TOMONLAMA BAHOLASH METODIKASI //Scienceproblems. uz. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 96-104. Shermatov G. K. Classification of Methods of Sports Wrestling, System //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 39-42.
4. Мухаметов А.М. (2021) Methodology for Normalizing Workload in Health Classes, european journal of life safety and stability, <http://www.ejlss.indexedresearch.org/>
5. Шерматов Ф.Қ. (2021) DYNAMICS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS WITH ONE AND TWO TIME COMPULSORY LESSONS, World Economics & Finance Bulletin (WEFB) <https://www.scholarexpress.net/>
6. Мухамметов, А.М. (2022). Научно-методические основы нормирования нагрузок в физкультурно-спортивном здравоохранении. Евразийский научный вестник, 8, 194-197.
7. Khurramovich, K. F. (2022). DEVELOPING A SET OF WELLNESS EXERCISES FOR MIDDLE AGED MEN (45-60 YEARS OLD) ACCORDING TO PHYSICAL PREPARATION. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(04), 165-169.
8. Alisherovich, T. F., & Toshboyeva, M. B. Innovative Pedagogical Activity: Content and Structure.
9. Tashpulatov Farkhad Alisherovich, METHODOLOGY OF COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION OF GAME ACTIVITY EFFICIENCY OF HANDBALL PLAYERS, 2023/1, ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES, 96-104, <https://doi.org/10.47390/1342V3I1Y2023N10>
10. Khurramovich, K. F. (2022). DEVELOPING A SET OF WELLNESS EXERCISES FOR MIDDLE AGED MEN (45-60 YEARS OLD) ACCORDING TO PHYSICAL PREPARATION. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(04), 165-169.
11. Khurramovich, K. F. (2022). METHODOLOGY OF WEIGHTLIFTING WITH ATHLETES. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(4), 1228-1233.
12. Karimov, F. X. (2022). Scientific and Methodological Bases of Normalization of Loads in Physical Education and Mass Sports-Health Training. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 2(2), 24-28.
13. Karimov, F. X. (2021). Plan Individual Fitness Training Programs for Middle-Aged Men. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630)*, 11, 238-244.
14. Каримов, Ф. Х. (2020). CLASSIFICATION, SYSTEM AND TERMS OF SPORT WRESTLING METHODS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION*, 1(4), 84-88.

- 15.Каримов, Ф. Х., & Ташпулатов, Ф. А. (2020). РЕСПУБЛИКАМИЗДАГИ ЮНОН-РИМ КУРАШИ БИЛАН ШУҒУЛЛАНУВЧИ ЎСМИРЛАРНИ ҚАРШИ ҲУЖУМ УСУЛЛАРИГА ЎРГАТИШ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ. ИННОВАЦИИ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИИ, (SI-2№ 4).
- 16.Каримов, Ф. Х. (2017). Физическая культура и её связь с общей культурой. Высшая школа, (4), 65-66.
- 17.Каримов, Ф. Х. (2017). Физическая культура и её связь с общей культурой. Высшая школа, (4), 65-66.
- 18.Karimov, F. K. (2022). Developing A Combination of Health Exercises for Middle-Aged Men Aged 45-60. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 8, 201-204.
- 19.Tashbaeva, M. (2022). Pedagogical Opportunities of Wrestling Sports in the Formation of a Sense of National Pride in Students. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 8, 213-216.
- 20.Toshboyeva, M. B. (2022). WELLNESS EXERCISES FOR HUMAN ENDURANCE DEVELOPMENT. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(4), 1214-1220.
- 21.Toshboyeva, M. B. (2022). Wrestling is a Kind of Sport with an Example of the First Training jar the Importance of the Formation of FastPaced Power Attributes with the Help of Moving Games. Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, 6, 291-294.
- 22.<https://iejrd.com/index.php/%20/article/view/2965>
- 23.<https://iejrd.com/index.php/%20/article/view/2962>.